

Open Call Collection OC-2024-1

Proposal Reference OC-2024-1-27454

Title: WikiSci: Making Expert Knowledge Public Using the Wikipedia Ecosystem

Acronym: WikiSci

Summary

Open knowledge infrastructure like Wikimedia form the basis of public knowledge and emerging technologies like AI, but scientists and other professionals do not engage with them in any systematic way. This allows disinformation to spread and neglects the 'third mission' of the university. While the academy struggles to revolutionise its communication systems, Wikimedia has led the way for decades, notably in promoting the use of Creative Commons licences. Our consortium of 16 universities, funders, museums, and NGOs seeks to promote systematic engagement from science to the open public knowledge base. To this end, we are gathering evidence of the impact of Wikimedia for open knowledge, developing internationally standard materials that can be used to train professionals in how to contribute, building incentives for contributing, and incubating disciplinary organisations that will adopt and support Wikipedia articles within their areas. Building these links has many benefits for both science and the public, e.g., having an unbiased source of more accurate medical information online, or as a trusted place where people can look for summaries of studies which have been described in the media. Year 1 gathers teams and develops materials to present the initiative. Year 2 preconfers an EOSC meeting to get central feedback and build relations. Year 3 does a trial conference for us and sends teams to their disciplinary conferences. Year 4 is our own conference in a target country to celebrate what we've done and plan for the future. The main outcomes of the grant will be papers and additional grant applications.

Key Expertise needed for evaluation

Media and communications

Media and communications, social aspects of information science and surveillance, socio-cultural communication

Media and communications

Databases, data mining, data curation, computational modelling

Computer and Information Sciences

Theoretical aspects of pervasive and ubiquitous computing

Educational sciences

Education: training, pedagogy, didactics

Keywords

Open Knowledge

Science Communication

Open Educational Resources

Open Data

Project Incubation

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TECHNICAL ANNEX

1. S&T EXCELLENCE

1.1. SOUNDNESS OF THE CHALLENGE

1.1.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE STATE OF THE ART

Public knowledge is threatened and we need better mechanisms for sharing expert knowledge.

The main challenge the action seeks to solve is how to more efficiently make scientific and expert knowledge of all kinds public, in order to combat misinformation and more efficiently distribute innovation throughout society. This is addressed in this COST Action by helping close knowledge gaps on Wikipedia, which is already where the world looks for information (Rasberry & Mietchen, 2024).

There has been a big push toward ‘opening’ science, but relatively few systematic efforts to communicate expert knowledge to the public. Some efforts have created e.g., open encyclopaedias, but these often struggle with sustainability, because they are starting from scratch. Meanwhile, Wikipedia has been leading the way for decades. Scientists and experts can, should, make their knowledge available where the public looks for it i.e., Wikipedia and lead the way in helping to improve this knowledge base. There are many opportunities for synergy, where existing Wikimedia infrastructure can solve problems for the academy, while also solving problems of Wikimedia (e.g., resources, high quality edits). The goal is to build these links by organising networking opportunities.

The basic argument of the proposal is that:

1. Wikipedia is where the public including Google and AI look for knowledge.
2. Science searches for better ways to make its knowledge open and accessible.
3. But, scientists and other experts do not systematically contribute to Wikipedia.

No matter whether this knowledge base is expert curated or not, the world is looking at it, and so in this sense it makes sense to make it good. Engaging academics and experts in general with this knowledge base will be good for everyone, since the academy lacks the public buy-in for its proposals while Wikimedia lacks high quality contributions, which science can provide. The Wikimedia Foundation led the way in e.g., incubating Creative Commons, and the EU should engage with it.

This COST Proposal addresses how to bridge these gaps through a number of working groups bringing together teams around self determined objectives. There exist many teams working in this direction, but they are divided by disciplinary and national boundaries, with a lack of specific platforms for organising action, also because it is volunteer run. The goal is to bring together people from different national and disciplinary backgrounds and give them time to organise amongst themselves.

Wikipedia is designated by the EU as one of the 20 very large online platforms (EU Digital Services Act, updated 02.09.2024), but Wikipedia is different from the other 19 VLOPs because it is a community-run non-profit website, conceived as a service for the public good rather than a product. The European Commission has recognized the impressive size and influence of Wikipedia and its relevance for digital competences in the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp), but it has not yet acknowledged its capacity and potential of implementing ideals which are European, such as democracy, participation, citizen engagement, volunteerism, openness, access to knowledge and information. **Our thesis is that engaging and building relationships between Europe and Wikimedia is essential for protecting and potentiating this open, public, knowledge source.**

There exists a yearly worldwide Wikimedia event called Wikimania which will be held in Paris 2026. Our first goal is to host a pre-conference for EU Science on Wikimedia at this event, also enabling the Action participants to attend that conference in general. The goal is to organise energy and solutions from within Wikimedia, and then to take these potentialities to an EOSC/ EU level digital infrastructure conference in 2027, again hosting a pre-conference. Presentation materials and e.g., a syllabus will be created for the event to receive feedback on, in particular from central European Actors. Year 3, the goal is to have a small/ trial conference of 'our own' while mainly sending teams of Action participants to their home communities e.g., international disciplinary conferences to present the materials and recruit people to e.g., disciplinary user groups which will maintain articles in those areas. Year 4, 2029, a larger WikiSci conference is organised in an Inclusiveness Target nation, celebrating, and setting goals for the future of the field and conference series.

1.1.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE CHALLENGE (MAIN AIM)

This project works to solve several main, inter-related, problems which can be solved by using the Wiki Ecosystem as an interface between scientific knowledge and public knowledge. These include:

There is a lack of infrastructure and communication between science and the public. There are many initiatives in science to change science communication, including open access, preprints, open data, but far fewer initiatives to link scientific knowledge and public knowledge, even though trust in science is falling. Such communication is critical because the media often does not have the nuance that new science demands. Using Wikipedia to communicate about fields/ particular papers is just one potential solution, and the goal is to bring together and support teams working on these issues.

New initiatives set up by scholars struggle to gain a foothold. Part of the reason for this lack of infrastructure is because the platforms scientists set up often struggle to be maintained. There do exist initiatives for Open Educational Resources (OERs), with examples being e.g., Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Scholarpedia, the Open Encyclopedia of Cognitive Science and many others. The problem is that they are trying to create their own platforms and struggling because they have to e.g., create their own websites, new communities, etc. (Buttliere, 2014). There exist at least 18 different Medical informational sources (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_medical_wikis). Each of these had to create their own website, backend development, and article for e.g., medicine, which is not ideal; we argue that the public will benefit more simply by using Wikipedia, which already has the infrastructure, public trust, good reputation, page rank and visitation that these websites need.

Wikipedia is the largest and most trusted public knowledge base in the world, but there do exist knowledge gaps. Wikipedia is one of the most viewed and trustworthy websites in the world (Konieczny, 2016). Still, gaps exist. If you look up your favorite episode of your favorite television show, you will most likely find a Wikipedia page for that episode. Conversely, if you look up your favourite scientific journal or research topic, or even specific papers that are among Altmetrics top 100 discussed online scientific papers (Altmetrics, 2020), there is a high chance that there is no Wikipedia page for it. This is a problem for public knowledge, because these papers are highly discussed in the media, often without the nuance or understanding the paper deserves. Unfortunately, when people go online to learn more about these articles, there sometimes does not exist a Wikipedia page for that article with clear non-biased information. This then allows for e.g., disinformation about science, since bad or misinformed actors are then the ones to set the record about that science. A few active good actors can manage these bad actors and the goal is to have most or all scientists contributing.

Many Wikimedia Initiatives work toward European and scientific goals, but there are few systematic efforts at the EU level to engage with the Wiki Ecosystem. Wikimedia is in many ways an exemplary VLOP, which can be learned from as the EU starts its own digital initiatives (e.g. the European Open Science Cloud; EOSC; McGranaghan, et al., 2021). The lack of existing engagement at the European level is apparent by searching e.g., for "Wikipedia" on the COST website. Only one Action mentions it (KNOWeSCAPE), and this action ended in 2017 (cost.eu/actions/TD1210/). At the same time, Wikimedia has many initiatives which mirror European concerns, e.g., the Wikimedia and Libraries User Group, WikiJournals platform (Shafee et al., 2018), Wikimedia Education, and WikiBooks. There are many potential synergies with European existing funded projects which can benefit from the collaboration and interoperability with the Wikimedia projects. This lack of systematic effort hinders open knowledge in general and allows e.g., misinformation to occur.

Scientists engaging with Wikimedia are often selected out of the scientific system. Even though academics engaging with Wikimedia is good for the world in general (Shafee, Mietchen, & Su, 2017), when a scientist engages with Wikimedia currently, they are spending time that they could be spending on conducting original research, publishing academic articles, and presenting their work at professional conferences. These are activities that are clearly legible to decision makers of e.g., tenure and promotion. Essentially everyone in the Wikimedia space knows someone who has suffered because they are e.g., organising Wikimedia edit-a-thons rather than editing a journal. The goal is to make contributing a valued output, also for grants and tenure outcomes.

The longer the sector remains in this fragmented, reactive state, the longer and more fragmentary public knowledge will remain, and the more susceptible public knowledge and future technologies like AI are to misinformation and lack of trust in science. The relevance and timeliness of the project comes from the growing understanding that expert knowledge including e.g., sciences and the humanities needs a better platform to make its knowledge public and the recognition that Wikipedia already has most or all of what is needed.

1.2. PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

1.2.1. APPROACH TO THE CHALLENGE AND PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

The main challenge is effectively communicating science to the public, thus preventing misinformation, guarding democracy, and increasing trust in science. The approach is to bring teams that are working on these problems from many stakeholder groups (Section 2.2.1) together to a dedicated space where projects can be incubated. The plan proposes first marshalling efforts in the Wikimedia Community Year 1, presenting them to central EU actors Year 2, rolling them out to the different disciplines and networks in Year 3 and reconstituting as a new community to set a path forward in Year 4.

Our approach is to bring teams and networks to a dedicated platform from which projects and collaborations can grow. This COST Action aims to bring the many teams working on these goals together in a dedicated forum, and provide them the resources they need to begin collaborations and develop grant projects in the future. One thing that is clear from attending many academic and Wikimedia conferences is that many teams are working in the same direction, for instance creating training materials for contributors. Instead of each team struggling to create their own, the goal of the COST Action is provide a platform from which some internationally standard materials can emerge.

To this end, the Action establishes a series of working groups, which will be tracks in a (pre)conference, which focus on particular goals and deliverables, as listed below.

1.2.2. OBJECTIVES

1.2.2.1. Research Coordination Objectives

The main aim of the Action is to make expert knowledge more publicly available, where the public looks for it, on e.g., Wikipedia. This Action builds on and brings together existing networks so that the Action can push forward in strategically coordinated ways.

To achieve these goals, the COST Action focuses on these Research Coordination Objectives (RCO):

RCO1: Understanding who is doing what currently, and our capacity to help them in their work.

The goal of RCO1 is to identify who is doing what and bring them into the action, to dedicated spaces and toward the working groups that match their stated goals and efforts. The action also expects to develop an extensive database of researchers working with Wikimedia from which future grants can be built. An early version of this database is located at meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Research:People

RCO2: Supporting experts in contributing by developing training materials and syllabi. One of the major goals of the network is to make it easier to contribute by providing internationally endorsed and standardised training materials on how and why to contribute. This RCO gathers materials, identifies best practices, and will create and trial example materials and e.g., syllabi and example assignments on how to train students in open knowledge and contributing to open knowledge sources.

RCO3: Identifying and creating metrics of credit, value, and impact for contributing to OERs.

One of the major inhibiting factors for open knowledge on e.g., Wikipedia is that academic decision

makers do not value it as legitimate output (Buttliere, Vetter, Ross, 2024). This objective is about identifying metrics and tools which can be used to indicate impact, that will help change it.

RCO4: Develop and facilitate interoperability between the Wikimedia ecosystem and EOSC. While scientists struggle to develop sustainable solutions to these problems, Wikimedia already has the infrastructure. The goal is to connect European Infrastructures with Wiki counterparts to share lessons, with a particular focus on Wikidata, EOSC and other repositories, licences and open tools.

RCO5: Provide a platform from which budding projects can grow. The point of the action is to enable others to network and help build their own research projects. Especially in year 3, mini-grants are prepared so that the teams can meet and plan the next phases of their projects at e.g., disciplinary conferences, presenting the Action to others and bringing people into the network.

RCO6: Strengthen public knowledge and set the trajectory of open knowledge for the future. The engagement of scientists and academics in contributing to Wikipedia and its ecosystem set the stage for a better public knowledge base in the future. While this project starts with science, the goal is of course to have professionals and experts in all fields make their knowledge open.

1.2.2.2. Capacity-building Objectives

CBO1: Establishing an international network supporting and facilitating effective synergies between open online collaborative projects and academia. The network provides time and meeting space for teammates working in the same direction to meet and plan. Success will be measured through the measurement of subgroup growth and engagement. This CBO will be measured through the number of projects, presentations, papers, and especially grants created.

CBO2: Supporting knowledge exchange to identify best practices and common pitfalls, spreading this institutional knowledge through the network. What works and what does not is identified and shared. The existing materials and best practices are gathered, documented, and selected to improve and translate the materials allowing for international standardisation. The success of this CBO can be measured through the quality of the materials created and the number of people who adopt them in their teaching, additionally the growth of these organizations.

CBO3: Supporting young researchers in learning digital competences with a specific attention to copyright, open science and contributing to OERs and the Wikimedia Ecosystem. More than just creating the syllabi, the goal is to actually teach students, and to receive feedback in so-called flipped classrooms, new wikis, and other studies designed to track impact. Materials are developed in Year 1, feedback is collected in Year 2, teaching starts in Years 3 & 4. The success of this CBO will be measured through the number of editors recruited, students taught, and impact achieved with them.

CBO4: Develop field specific user groups to build out articles in their areas. A major goal of the Action will be to bring together and strengthen (inter)disciplinary user groups. Similar to the educational materials, the goal will be to identify best practices to help these organisations grow. Target user groups include WikiMedicine, WikiBiology, and WikiMath, which also demonstrates the various levels of organisation of these groups, from relatively informal user groups, to projects, and registered non-profit organisations. The success of this CBO can be measured through the number of new users, and articles edited.

CBO5: Formalise the Wikimedians in Residence programme and establish collaborations. The Wikimedian in Residence (WiR) program has seen major success at large, national, European museums. These efforts will focus on supporting the current Wikimedian in Residence Exchange Network, providing both a European meeting point and a way to identify new communities. The goal is to bring representatives of this network to the table, with the explicit goal of supporting them in professionalising so that it can go beyond the biggest museums to medium and small ones.

Figure 1: Demonstrating how some of the main Research Coordination Objectives (RCO) and Capacity Building Objectives (CBO) relate.

CBO6: Build example materials for how research funders might include OERs in their grant outcomes. Making it so that contributing to Wikimedia and knowledge communication is a part of the grant making and awards process is a major goal of the Action, which also reflects efforts to reward open practices during hiring (Chambers, Lebel et al., 2018). The goal will be to build examples for how funders and universities can work contributing to Wikimedia into their evaluation processes. Progress here can be measured through the number of funders using them, & downloads of the examples.

CBO7: Facilitating inclusion and diversity, triggering gender balance, and providing opportunities for young researchers, in particular from Inclusiveness Target Nations. Both the COST Action and Wikipedia are focused on Inclusiveness. The activities are designed to allow opportunities for young researchers, especially from COST Inclusion Nations through events and training opportunities. Half of our working groups are from target inclusion nations, and there is a focus on ECR, gender, and minority issues. Not only is the grant based in a COST Target Inclusion nation, we intend to focus our efforts in terms of grant making on Target Inclusiveness nations, also and in particular to Early Career Researchers of Minority status.

2. NETWORKING EXCELLENCE

2.1. ADDED VALUE OF NETWORKING IN S&T EXCELLENCE

2.1.1. ADDED VALUE IN RELATION TO EXISTING EFFORTS AT EUROPEAN AND/OR INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

While there exist some collaborations between Europeana and Wikimedia, e.g., the Wikibase and the EU Knowledge Graph (linkedopendata.eu/wiki/), few explicit and structured co-operations exist.

AV1: Networking disciplinarily and nationally fragmented research and action fields There exist many labs and initiatives related to Wikimedia, but there exist to our knowledge no officially EU funded networks or projects concerning the relationship between Wikimedia and Science. This is also demonstrated in the low engagement of COST Actions with Wikipedia, with only one cost action being associated with it. The goal is to bring together teams across national and disciplinary boundaries to increase scientific contributions to Wikimedia.

AV2: Providing mechanisms and a platform for coordination and collaboration Lack of progress in this area can be attributed to a few key problems including that Wikipedia is often run by volunteers, with only limited, non-governmental funding, which has been an inhibiting factor. This COST Action contributes to establishing a platform from which academic projects and collaborations can grow, and to use meeting opportunities provided by the Action to help incubate these projects at an international level in ways that are sustainable and successful into the future.

AV3: Internationalising efforts at Wikimedia and in Wikimedia Education While Wikimedia has quietly been working toward European Goals, there have been few formal engagements from the European side. Wikimedia Europe and various country level groups exist, which also create Wikimedia versions in local languages, but there are few systematic engagements, also demonstrated in the problem section by showing that no active COST Actions mention Wikipedia. This lack of international structures also hinders progress, especially in small language versions of Wikipedia, which is a particular problem for the EU. The COST Action provides the opportunity to systematise these efforts, especially as they relate to training materials. The goal with these series of events is to make it easier to train new contributors.

AV4: Strengthening non-English knowledge bases through systematic efforts One of the largest advantages of using the Wikimedia Ecosystem is that it is already built across many European languages. This is in contrast to existing initiatives or other new initiatives from researchers which almost exclusively exist in English and rarely have plans for implementing other languages until some unspecified point in the future. Wikimedia already has many language user groups, which also contain researchers in their nations (i.e., the participants in this Action), which brings value for the network.

2.2. ADDED VALUE OF NETWORKING IN IMPACT

2.2.1. SECURING THE CRITICAL MASS, EXPERTISE AND GEOGRAPHICAL BALANCE WITHIN THE COST MEMBERS AND BEYOND

The key of the Action is that we are bridging many national and disciplinary networks, as well as different stakeholder groups like the universities, libraries, museums, repositories etc in order to create a dedicated platform where we can work and plan together. There exist many organizations working in this direction but these are in almost all cases disciplinarily and nationally bound, making it difficult to organise at e.g., the European level.

To this extent we have leveraged Wikimedia Europe and the Central and Eastern European user groups and granting committees to identify the highest impact researchers we can find within the Full COST and Target Inclusion Countries. This ensures that we are extending the network and providing the geographical balance that is needed for a truly successful COST Action.

The granting activities focus on providing researchers and community leaders in the target nations with the funding and opportunities they need to pursue the work they are doing. This is also indicated by the fact that many of the Working Groups and Action Management Committee members are from Inclusion countries.

The goal is to bring especially those taking part in the Action from these Target Inclusion nations to these excellent conferences through the pre-conferencing mechanism. Given that each working group will develop a track in the pre-conference, it gives these researchers some dedicated space to meet, talk about, and plan their next projects and grants, as well as get feedback

The goal of this series of conferences and trainings is to bring those working on this topic together. In the first year to marshal the resources and solutions of the Wikimedia Community. In the second year, to take these potential solutions onto the EU stage for central feedback. In the third year, to distribute this knowledge gained to the different disciplines that we come from. Finally, in the fourth year, to come back together to plan for the future. There are several unique value propositions from this COST Action that we describe below:

AV1: Bringing together national organizations of Wikimedia. Many national organizations are represented, and working toward the same goals, but not working together and pushing as effectively as possible at e.g., the European level. The goal here is to bring them together and incubate actions.

AV2: Organising interdisciplinary action within the academy. Similarly, there exist many disciplinary organisations (e.g., Wikimedice, Wikiphilosophy, WikiMath, WikiPsy), that are already engaged, but are not yet working together to the fullest extent possible. The Action is creating space for the projects.

AV3: Travelling to established communities as a group brings force and credibility. The structure of the series of conferences is built to interact with the relevant stakeholders. Year 1 mobilises the Wikimedia community to identify potentialities. Year 2 brings these solutions to Central EU actors at e.g., the EOSC Symposium 2026 to get feedback. Year 3 goes to disciplinary conferences with the solutions, Year 4 establishes the community.

AV4: Providing opportunities for Project Incubation, especially in non central communities. One of the biggest goals of the action is to stimulate especially in non-english knowledge bases. To this extent we have a strong focus on e.g., building internationally standard materials that can be used as a basis for e.g, translation. We are creating some platform explicitly for those who do not get the credit they deserve. This is also partially the point of creating these series of awards for open science.

2.2.2. INVOLVEMENT OF STAKEHOLDERS

Major Stakeholders of this project include:

MST1: The public and its knowledge base. Making high quality knowledge more accessible is key, especially in the Inclusion Target Countries, and linguas, which are often neglected in efforts to make scientific information available, which focus on the Global South (e.g. Rasberry et al., 2022).

MST2: Universities and science. Many initiatives in science look for ways to make scientific knowledge more available to the public, the goal here is to use existing infrastructure i.e., Wikis in new and more productive ways for scientific communication.

MST3: Professional Academic Organizations. Professional organisations often struggle with how to convey the importance of their topic, along with the latest findings in the field. By contributing to Wikipedia, these organisations can make their information available where people actually look at it.

MST4: Libraries. Making content more available is key to the third mission of universities and e.g., trust in science. Libraries have in some ways led the way with the open access movement, and they are also helping lead the way here, with activities in a number of the working groups below.

MST5: (Research) Museums. Research Museums and museums more generally are also quite involved in especially working group 5, and in relation to the professionalisation of the Wikimedians in residence, which we hope to take to medium and small museums in addition to large ones.

MST6: NGOs/ Wikimedia. Science on Wikimedia suffers from a lack of expert contributions and frankly governmental level resources, to ensure that the knowledge base is healthy and defended.

MST7: Hospitals/ professional organizations The goal is to reach beyond 'pure' science and to make Wikimedia a high quality knowledge base in general also for e.g., Medically relevant information. Especially in non-central communities, resources are not there and Wikimedia is of the first information a person will see.

MST8: Governments/ Funders Wikimedia has been leading the way in terms of e.g., Creative Commons, Open Data, Wikidata, European Open Science, we think the EU can learn valuable things from these groups. The goal of the action is to bridge this divide and actuate all potentials both at Wikimedia but also at the EOSC and other initiatives.

Each of these Stakeholder Groups are represented within the network and we intend to continue to grow out these groups especially in terms of funders and political decision makers over the 4 years.

Figure 2: Relationship of Major Stakeholders (MST)s and the project.

3. IMPACT

3.1. IMPACT TO SCIENCE, SOCIETY AND COMPETITIVENESS, AND POTENTIAL FOR INNOVATION/BREAKTHROUGHS

3.1.1. SCIENTIFIC, TECHNOLOGICAL, AND/OR SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACTS (INCLUDING POTENTIAL INNOVATIONS AND/OR BREAKTHROUGHS)

The minimal expected outputs (O) of this COST Action, ranked from specificity to generality, include:

- O1:** GDPR aware database of potential collaborators for grants, which will make it easier to network.
- O2:** Overview and understanding of the evidence relating to the open impact that Wikimedia has.
- O3:** Syllabi and teaching materials that can be used to teach academics how to effectively contribute.
- O4:** Understanding of what metrics are valued as indicators of contributing to the Wiki ecosystem.
- O5:** Materials based on a survey of best practices and largest pitfalls for organizations to use.
- O6:** Multi-tiered TOPS style guidelines that organizations can sign onto and work toward.
- O7:** More impact trackable science content on Wikipedia and other OER platforms.
- O8:** More open and available scientific knowledge.
- O9:** More trusted public and scientific knowledge, also in relation to, e.g., misinformation.
- O10:** A network and series of projects and grants aimed at securing/ furthering WikiSci

The Key Innovation, Outcome, or Breakthrough will be researchers sharing their knowledge on Wikimedia, which in turn will lead to a higher quality public knowledge base, a more informed citizenship, and more trust in science. This will be facilitated both through the meetings and the materials developed there, which will also focus on harbouring equity and equality in the area.

3.2. MEASURES TO MAXIMISE IMPACT

3.2.1. KNOWLEDGE CREATION, TRANSFER OF KNOWLEDGE AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT

In the traditional bibliometric sense, we will count presentations, papers, the productivity of scientific trips, and grants as the impacts. But in a more general sense, it should be considered the knowledge that will be made open through the trainings and new edits that are brought to Wikimedia and other OERs. Already we can confidently say that the contributions that our Action participants have made to public knowledge number at least in the hundreds of millions of views, click throughs, students and people in general learning things from the platform that is Wikimedia.

The goal of the Action is to bring people together, help with the transfer of knowledge, and especially provide career development opportunities for Women, ECRs and those from the Target Inclusiveness Nations. We commit to spending at least 50% of the budget to support researchers and innovators from Inclusiveness Target Countries, focusing especially on Early Career Researcher's mobility and ability to be present and take part in the COST Action.

3.2.2. PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND/OR EXPLOITATION AND DIALOGUE WITH THE GENERAL PUBLIC OR POLICY

From the start, the action is about better communicating science with the public and policy makers, and the idea is to make it easier to disseminate science in general, not only the outputs of this Action.

Dissemination, exploitation, and dialogue are built into the plans of the action going from the Wikimedia to the European, and then disciplinary communities to talk about the plan and recruit collaborators. Beyond standard journal papers, we also expect to create standard syllabi and teaching materials which can be used to train new editors. If we are effective in engaging scientists, the impact will be substantial, and of a large value to public knowledge in general.

We also expect to develop the GDPR aware database of researchers working on this topic organized by the country, topics, and organizations that they work with. This will make it easier for researchers to find each other in the future when they want to undertake a project. Obviously the conferences we will be building will also be of immeasurably high value in terms of the connections that are made and the projects that are incubated. We also expect to build international collaborations within the Wikimedia community, such that future collaboration is easier across the network.

The milestones are grouped by year (M1, M2, M3, M4) and working group/ objective (e.g., M1.1, M1.2). This list does not include the COST arranged first meeting, nor the final meeting.

M1: Hosting first Action meeting as a pre conference at Wikimania Paris 2026. Each of the working groups will be responsible for presenting their first milestone at the first year meeting. This will be done within the context of a half day session or symposium at the two day preconference, giving the teams time to both present as well as plan how they will marshal potentialities at Wikimania.

M1.1: Presentation calling for examples outlining the value of Wikimedia potentials to science.

M1.2: Development of/ presentation on an initial syllabi and materials that can be used internationally.

M1.3: Development of/ presentation on potential metrics for indicating the value of contributing.

M1.4: Demonstrating the use of Wikimedia to host journal content e.g., genus, paper summaries.

M1.5: Surveying disciplinary organisations and developing some common ground between them.

M2: Hosting second Action meeting as a preconference at EOSC meeting 2027. Each of the working groups will be responsible for presenting their second milestone at the EU/ EOSC meeting. They additionally will be expected to help organise one of the tracks at the conference, also to present on their working group's progress throughout the year. This also gives them a chance to plan.

M2.1: Presentation of the argument at an EU/ EOSC in relation to Wikimedia.

M2.2: Presentation of the syllabi and materials created during Y1, gathering feedback.

M2.3: Publication of a white paper outlining Wikimedia Impact Metrics and Tools.

M2.4: Example articles for how summaries of scientific articles can be put on Wikipedia.

M2.5: Identify what museums and funders most want from Wikimedians in Residence

M3: Hosting a small conference for us and sending teams to disciplinary conferences. The third year of the Action is focused on trialling a specific WikiSci conference, but mostly focused on taking the materials developed and tested in years 1 and 2 and presenting them at disciplinary conferences. The focus for grant making will be to especially send teams of target inclusion and COST Full member researchers to present the work together, for instance as a symposium.

M3.1: Presentation of the internationally standardised materials to the disciplinary conferences.

M3.2: Development of standard materials on how journals can better interact with Wikimedia.

M3.3: Presentation of Wikimedia Impact Tools at disciplinary organisations.

M3.4: Using standard impact metrics to demonstrate the value of Wikimedia for GLAMS.

M3.5: Develop a white paper about user group best practices for science, with example structures.

M3.6: Awarding a series of (5-10) mini grants so that teams can organise disciplinary symposia.

M4: A specific conference in a target country, to solidify the position of WikiSci. The goal of the fourth year is to take the energy that was cultivated during the other conferences and host a conference of our own, also based on the experiences learned in organising the other (pre)conferences. The main goals of this conference will be to present on what was done and especially to focus on grants that will sustain the networks built into the future. Thus, a major focus will be on potential future avenues, and identifying opportunities that various actors in the network might want to apply for together.

M4.1: Training the trainers type event for people on how to argue for Wikimedia and open knowledge.

M4.2: Presentation on Wikimedia Impact Metrics a paper about the impact achieved so far.

M4.3: Presentation about the progress and outcomes of journals engaging with Wikimedia thus far.

M4.4: White paper and presentation published on the impact of Wikimedia for GLAMs

M4.5: Presentation and meeting of various user groups developed during M3 conferences.

M4.6: Establishment and development of additional grant opportunities for the network to apply to.

Table 1: Description of the relations between Working groups, Years, and Milestones

WikiSci Summary	Y1: Wikimania Paris	Y2: EOSC meeting	Y3: Disciplinary groups	Y4: WikiSci Conference
WG1: Network building	M1.1: Call for CoOps	M2.1: Present Argument	M3.1: Publish Paper	M4.1: Major Networking
WG2: WEW/ Training	M1.2: Gather materials	M2.2: Basic Demo/ Test	M3.2: Official Rollout	M4.2: Train Trainers
WG3: WIM/ Metrics	M1.3: First Demo	M2.3: Show Impact	M3.3: Paper Published	M4.3: Demo WIM/ WIT
WG4: Jrnls/ Funders	M1.4: Gathering groups	M2.4: Example CoOps	M3.4: Pilot Testing	M4.4: TOP Guidelines
WG5: GLAMs/ WiRs	M1.5: Planning action	M2.5: Gather Data	M3.5: Demo Impact	M4.5: Publish Big Impact
All teams:	M1.6: Conf Proceedings	M2.6: Conf Proceedings	M3.6: Apply Grants	M4.6: Plan Future

4. IMPLEMENTATION

4.1. COHERENCE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF THE WORK PLAN

4.1.1. DESCRIPTION OF WORKING GROUPS, TASKS AND ACTIVITIES

Each working group contributes a particular perspective, and approaches the problem differently, and thus makes up an important component of the overall Action Plan.

WG1: Demonstrating/ arguing for the impact of the Wikimedia Ecosystem for open knowledge.

The major goal of the Action is to make the argument that the Wikimedia Ecosystem has significant value to offer to EU scientists, humanists, and professionals more generally. Thus, WG1 gathers examples of good practice from research teams and analyses the impact of using Wikimedia for science. WG1 will also be the sort of welcoming group for newcomers to the group, since it will be heavily focused on networking to find the evidence and potential solutions. This WG is related to Deliverables (Ds) 1, 2, and 5 in cooperation with all Major Stakeholders (MSTs).

M1.1: Gathering projects and people to make the argument that Wikimedia is useful for EU science.

M2.1: Preparation of example presentation slides making the argument to be presented in Year 2

M3.1: Contribute to each of the conference proceedings by organising a session at the conference.

M4.1: Present the argument at WikiSci and present some vision of the next steps for the Action.

D2: Paper making the argument that Wikimedia is good and necessary for public knowledge.

D8: Contribute to each of the conference proceedings by organising a session at the conferences.

WG2: Creation of example training materials and syllabi to help trainers and trainees.

One of the first questions people ask is how to contribute, and many people feel a lack of confidence to contribute. WG2 is focused on making it easier to contribute by helping trainee(r)s with standard example materials on how to effectively contribute. The goal is to gather various materials used now, and standardise them across the EU. This is in some way an extension of Wikimedia Education, which is quite exclusively North America based to something more like Wikimedia Education Worldwide. This WG is related to Ds 1, 3, and 8, with MSTs 2, 3, and 4.

M1.2: Gather teams and materials creating educational materials to identify best practices.

M2.2: Present first materials and syllabi that can be used to train on how to contribute.

M3.2: Development of presentation materials/ papers which will be used to train newcomers.

M4.2: Train the trainers type event at the dedicated WikiSci Conference.

D3: Internationally standard example materials for trainee(er)s on how to contribute.

D8: Contribute to each of the conference proceedings by organising a session at the conferences.

WG3: Identifying and creating reward mechanisms for communicating science Wikimedia.

One of the major problems with getting academics to contribute to Wikimedia is that they do not get professional credit. The goal of WG3 is then to identify potential metrics of contribution and to at least begin building these metrics and making them available to Wikimedians and researchers at large. This will also involve the creation of a series of Wikimedia/ open science related rewards that will be rolled out especially during Year 3 when we send the delegations to the discipline specific conferences.

M1.3: Identify/create metrics of contribution so that academics can get 'credit' for contributing.

M2.3: Development of presentation materials that will be used to teach these metrics.

M3.3: Contribute to each of the disciplinary conferences through the exemplar slides.

M4.3: Present WIM/WIT at the conference, so that Action Participants can indicate their impact.

D4: Development/ publication of Wikimedia Impact Metrics and the Wikimedia Impact Tracker.

D8: Contribute to each of the conference proceedings by organising a session at the conferences.

WG4: Building out WikiSci by linking Wikimedia platforms and scholarly communities.

A major goal of the action is to get highly discussed science on Wikimedia platforms. Essentially everyone we have talked to has agreed that at least those studies often discussed in the media (for instance recognized in the Altmetric top 100), should probably be on Wikipedia as a place for unbiased information. To this end, WG4 works with journals and publishers to make their content available on Wikimedia as it is published, for instance when a new species is discovered, in biology, putting its images onto Wikimedia Commons and creating relevant Wikidata/Wikispecies items for it.

M1.4: White paper about the involvement of journals with Wikipedia so that their content is accessible.

M2.4: Create TOPS style guidelines on how journals and organisations can contribute.

M3.4: Contribute to each of the conference proceedings by organising a session at the conference.

M4.4: Train The trainers type event on how to get experts contributing at WikiSci Conference.

D5: Example materials that funders and decision makers can use to encourage contributions.

D6: TOP type guidelines for GLAMs/ organizations to buy into.

D8: Contribute to each of the conference proceedings by organising a session at the conferences.

WG5: Highlighting the value for GLAMs & empowering Wikimedians in Residence program.

Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Universities, and Museums (GLAMs) – including universities with their academic libraries, archives and museums - can also benefit from engaging with Wikimedia, by making their archives available on the platform and involving their experts in sharing and disseminating specialistic knowledge. Moreover, GLAMs work with Wikimedia projects to ensure that these platforms offer the best information about them, about their goals and missions, improving access to their knowledge and collections. The goal is to bring together efforts in these areas, also in relation to the Wikimedian in residence programme, which involves an expert of Wikipedia and the Wikimedia projects as a resident at the institution and it has been a great success for many large public museums, libraries, archives and universities in Europe and around the world. The goal is to formalise these programmes and to help spread it to more institutions. This will be done by linking researchers at GLAMs already working to share more of their resources publicly on Wikimedia, to show the added impact of these materials when openly available via the Wikimedia ecosystem.

M1.5: White paper demonstrating the value of making collections and data available online.

M2.5: Create materials that can be used to convince GLAMs to engage.

M3.5: Contribute to each of the conference proceedings by organising a session at the conference.

M4.5: Highlight and award Journal and funder involvement at the WikiSci Conference.

D7: Paper demonstration of the power of making materials open for GLAUMs.

D8: Contribute to each of the conference proceedings by organising a session at the conferences.

4.1.2. DESCRIPTION OF DELIVERABLES AND TIMEFRAME

This grant will support the development of several expected outputs, including a series of conferences, papers, and grants related to building the Wikimedia-Academic bond.

D1: Paper demonstrating the value that the Wikimedia Ecosystem can bring to EU Science. The goal of WG1 and the action in general is to make the argument that science should engage more with Wikimedia. Thus, Deliverable 2 is a perspective paper laying out the argument and potential solutions that we identify, especially in year 1. The goal is to have this paper out during Year 2, and to have essentially the Action endorse it, also as an opening for the meeting with the EOSC community.

D3: Internationally standard example materials for trainee(s) on how to contribute. The major objective of WG2 is to develop materials that will be used to train professionals in how to contribute. Many teams create materials in e.g., their languages now, the goal is to standardise them. These materials will be trialled in Year 2, at the EOSC conference, edited given the feedback we receive, and then rolled out during Year 3 to the disciplinary groups and the general public in Year 4.

D4: Development/ publication of Wikimedia Impact Metrics and the Wikimedia Impact Tracker. WG3 is focused on developing reward mechanisms for scientists and D4 corresponds to this throughout the grant. The idea is to identify how Wikimedians and Academics want to indicate the impact they are having, and centralise these metrics into the Wikimedia Impact Tracker rolled out during Year 2, and introduced to students in Years 3 and beyond.

D5: Example materials that funders and decision makers can use to encourage contributions. Alongside a paper aimed at getting journals and universities to signal their commitment, we intend to release some example materials and ways that funders and governments can encourage contributing. This will be for instance, example wording which can be used in grant calls, as well as a few funding agencies pilot testing to see how it works and if there are problems.

D6: TOP type guidelines for GLAMs/ Universities/ organizations to buy into. WG4 focuses on bringing in Journals and Universities by providing them with adoption materials and examples of success. One of the most name recognizable initiatives in the last years was the Transparency and Openness guidelines (TOP Guidelines: Nosek et al., 2016) for how organisations could encourage change in e.g., making datasets available. The goal is to follow this example, with three levels of engagement with Wikipedia and Open Knowledge. This again is built so that a first draft can be presented in Year 2, receive feedback and then be rolled out the following years.

D7: Paper demonstration of the power of making materials open for GLAMs. WG5 focuses on harnessing the existing research and Wikimedians in Residence at e.g., major European Universities, to demonstrate the value of Wikimedia. This will be focused on using the Wikimedia Impact Metrics created as a part of WG3, and will bring together several teams already working in this area to do a larger cross disciplinary and national projects to focus the research area and direction.

D8: Series of conference reports summarising what was presented and the progress of WGs. The main *Actions* will be a series of preconferences aimed at providing a platform from which other projects can grow. Thus, the major outcomes are e.g., the presentation materials and conference papers which will be published online as a summary of the conference. These conferences will be maximised in terms of impact and attendance by pre conferencing prominent meetings in the relevant areas. The booklets will be put on relevant preprint servers e.g., Zenodo, the OSF, Wikibooks.

D9-X: A series of grant applications, and research projects coming out of them. The point of the Action is to establish the research priority as well as develop a number of other grants and projects that come out of the networks we build. To this end, we expect to submit at least one additional grant proposal associated with the Action, per year, though we expect more than this.

4.1.3. RISK ANALYSIS AND CONTINGENCY PLANS

Size of the network There are a number of specific risks to the Action, many of which are related to the size of the network and our ambition. On the one hand, the number of working groups means that there is a high chance of people having to leave the project due to changing positions, having children, or retiring. Conversely, the larger number of Working Groups increases the chances that even if one of the working groups encounters trouble, something will still get done and at least some of the working groups are likely to succeed. This is especially true since many WGs are in progress in some way.

Our team has taken steps to reduce the risks especially of the network failing by identifying a core team that is interested in these topics, and ensuring that the working groups are aligning with what the teams are already doing. *In this sense, the project is not that much asking people to do things they are not doing already, but rather more about providing a platform from which these projects can grow.*

Intractability of impacting science communication Probably the largest risk is that we are unable to substantially impact science communication and the relationship between science and Wikimedia. Changing how academics work is proving to be substantially difficult, unless it is good for the researchers themselves. In this sense, we feel that focusing on the incentives, and fostering groups so that nobody is having to do it alone, is important. Already projects are coming out of the network, so things not happening is not much of a risk.

Introducing biases to Wikipedia and the public knowledge base Another risk that becomes substantial, especially if we are successful, is the possibility of introducing biases due to the link between individual scientific outcomes and contributing. It is well known that some scientists cheat in terms of citation metrics, and bringing such people in the Wikipedia community, which is volunteer run, risks creating issues also with the presentation of knowledge in general. If Wikipedia is taken more seriously by the academic community, there will be many people who wish to go there and endorse their work to the detriment of e.g., brevity and notability.

Conflict of interest and the general knowledge base. Wikipedia articles do not 'have authors'. While this can also be a barrier for academic authors that want to get credit for their contributions (why we are building WIT and WIMs), it creates the potential to put one's potentially biased ideas out there as **the truth.** Tying editing to one's career outcomes increases the potential for problems because now those 'bad actors' are incentivized for this action which is difficult to stop. There are strong norms about not writing about one's own work due to such biases, but also there is an argument where sometimes literally they wrote the paper so who understands it better. The good news is that the Wikimedia community already has good standards and guidelines on such issues given its decades of being a hotbed for political disputes and edit wars. We are also taking this into account when developing the metrics. There is still work to do though, because some concessions must be made to recognized experts, and distrust of 'experts' is a real thing in Wikipedia.

The most likely risk is that some papers get stuck in review, and for this we intend to be open and transparent, also trying to take advantage of e.g., the WikiJournals and WikiBooks systems where it is deemed beneficial for the project. Establishing WikiJournals for disciplines for bachelor's studies for instance could be of great benefit to all parties involved, but there is no initiative or money for such actions today. The WikiJournals system exists but it struggles to get taken seriously, lacking funding, meanwhile EU science searches for new ways to publish and disseminate its knowledge.

If any risk becomes of serious threat, or any Working Group encounters a major obstacle, we will deliberate on it internally, and if needed bring on the broad network of universities, Wikimedia initiatives and affiliates, the COST team, and other appropriate EU authorities as needed.

In general, we have significant buy-in already, with 16 CoOrganizers on the initial grant submission, and thus look to better organise ourselves. Already the project is achieving outcomes in terms of additional grants from within the initial network.

4.1.4. GANTT DIAGRAM

The Gantt Diagram outlines the approximate dates of the deliverable for each of the working groups, including D1: the conference and meetings schedule, and D8: The facilitation of further grant writing and project creation. The progression of the deliverables also demonstrates in some way how they build on each other, for instance the organizational guidelines paper should point to the impact metrics and standard training materials created as a part of D2 and D3.

WikiSci Gantt Chart	Y1				Y2				Y3				Y4			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4												
Kickoff Meeting	█															
D1: MC and WG meetings			█		█		█		█		█		█		█	
M1: Wikimedia (pre)conference		█	█													
M2: European (pre)conference					█	█	█									
M3: Disciplinary conferences									█	█	█	█				
M4: Building our own conference													█	█	█	
D2: Paper making the argument			█	█												
D3: Standard training materials			█		█	█										
D4: Impact metrics/ tracker						█	█	█								
D5: TOP Style Guidelines							█	█	█							
D6: Funders/ Journals materials								█	█	█	█					
D7: Disciplinary awards/ groups										█	█	█				
D8: Further grants and projects													█	█	█	
Initial grants within original team		█	█	█												
Facilitation of 3-X medium grants					█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
Facilitation of 1+ major EU grants										█	█	█	█	█	█	
Final Conference																█
Reporting and monitoring				█	█			█	█			█	█		█	█

References

American Society for Cell Biology. (2012). San Francisco declaration on research assessment (DORA).

Buttliere, B. T. (2014). Using science and psychology to improve the dissemination and evaluation of scientific work. *Frontiers in computational neuroscience*, 8, 82.

Buttliere, B., Vetter, M., Ross, S., (2024). Developing Wikimedia Impact Metrics as a Sociotechnical Solution for Encouraging Funder/ Academic Engagement. *Wikimedia Research*. https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Grant_s:Programs/Wikimedia_Research_Fund/Developing_Wikimedia_Impact_Metrics_as_a_Sociotechnical_Solution_for_Encouraging_Funder/_Academic_Engagement

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). The agreement, 2022. URL <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>. Unofficial Report.

Digital Botanical Gardens Initiative Consortium. (2022). The Digital Botanical Gardens Initiative. Manubot. <https://www.dbgi.org/>

DORA. San francisco declaration on research assessment. Technical report, DORA, 2012. URL <https://https://sfdora.org/>

Glammons (2024). Resilient, sustainable and participatory practices: Towards the GLAMs of the commons – <https://glammons.eu/>

GSRMI (2018). The Transformative Potential of Research in Museums <https://www.leibniz-forschungsmuseen.de/gsrmi-2022>

Konieczny, P. (2016). Teaching with Wikipedia in a 21 st -century classroom: Perceptions of Wikipedia and its educational benefits. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67(7), 1523–1534. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23616>.

McGranaghan, E., Klein, S., Cameron, A., Young, E., Schonfeld, S., Higginson, A., Ringuette, R., Halford, A., Bard, C., Narock, A., & Thompson, B., (2021). The need for a Space Data Knowledge Commons. <https://knowledgestructure.pubpub.org/pub/space-knowledge-commons/release/2>

Myrtchen, S., (2022). *Mathematical Problems of Computer Science* 55, 00--00, 2021.

Nosek, B. A., Alter, G., Banks, G. C., Borsboom, D., Bowman, S., Breckler, S., ... & DeHaven, A. C. (2016). Transparency and openness promotion (TOP) guidelines.

Penev, L., Hagedorn, G., Mietchen, D., Georgiev, T., Stoev, P., Sautter, G., ... & Erwin, T. (2011). Interlinking journal and wiki publications through joint citation: Working examples from ZooKeys and Plazi on Species-ID. *ZooKeys*, (90), 1.

Racheva, V., (2012). Sofia Zoo and Bulgarian Wikipedians/Sofia Zoo Powered by Wikimedia. https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Grants:PEG/Sofia_Zoo_and_Bulgarian_Wikipedians/Sofia_Zoo_Powered_by_Wikimedia/Report

Raspberry, L., Tibbs, S., Hoos, W., Westermann, A., Keefer, J., Baskauf, S. J., ... & Mietchen, D. (2022). WikiProject clinical trials for wikidata. *medRxiv*, 2022-04.

ReCreating Europe (2021) GLAM Definition <https://recreating.eu/stakeholders/wp5-glam/>,

Shafee, T., Mietchen, D., & Su, A. I. (2017). Academics can help shape Wikipedia. *Science*, 357(6351), 557-558.

Wikimedian in Residence Exchange Network.

https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Wikimedians_in_Residence_Exchange_Network

COST Mission and Policies

The WikiSci Project supports the COST mission and Policies through a number of concrete steps.

COST's mission to 'help Europe address scientific, technological, and societal challenges by providing networking opportunities for researchers and innovators' perfectly describes the action and mission of the Action in that it provides networking and project incubation opportunities for a number of interrelated projects closely linked to scientific, technological, and societal challenges.

The project develops European-based scientific and technological networks, especially within the context of communicating science to the public. The goal of the Action is to support researchers who are working to make European Science more available to the (European) Public. This is a particularly European problem since it has so many languages spoken within its borders. Wikimedia serves this mission due to its many language Versions. Thus we feel this project fits in a particularly European way to the COST Mission.

The goal of the project is to integrate all of the stakeholders in Figure 2, intensifying links between scientific communities, museums, libraries, Wikimedia, and the public more generally. The goal is to make higher quality knowledge more open and available, especially using the outstanding infrastructure that the Wikimedia foundation and the Wikimedia Community build over the last 20 or so years. This is also reflected in the wide range of participants.

The project is quite interdisciplinary and international. The Action has researchers from across the medical, social, historical, biological, chemical, and medical sciences. Additionally it has representatives from over a dozen countries, most of which are on the Inclusiveness list. The biggest strength of the Wikimedia community is that from everywhere and every scientific discipline. This grant application process has already brought to light many latent needs and desires in the community, and many potential collaborations have already been initiated.

The project has a strong focus on the Inclusiveness Target Nations. Another major benefit of the Action is that the Target Inclusion Nations are strongly represented, with 66% of the proposers coming from Target nations. Additionally, every Working Group has a (co) organiser from an Inclusion Nation, and the entire project in general is being submitted from an inclusion nation. Especially the hosting of the project in an inclusion nation we feel will serve the project because e.g., the money for administration will go farther, which in turn should benefit the outcomes of the Action in general. We are strongly committed to spending 50% of the budget on Inclusion nations, and we intend to focus the use of funds on supporting inclusion nation researchers.

Strong focus on engaging Youths and Early Career Researchers. While the project has so far focused on identifying e.g., the group leaders to join the Action, the goal will be to include many young researchers in the proceedings of the action. We hope and intend that most of the funding will be spent on bringing young members of the community that are not as established to the pre-conferences, also giving them opportunities to present their work to an international and interdisciplinary audience.

Intention and Purpose surrounding Gender. The project is pushing for change in regards to Gender, and is dedicated toward putting women in positions of real power, rather than just administrative roles. In this sense, more than half of the Working groups are (co) led by women. Additionally, our grant making and resource distribution strategies will benefit women. This is also reflected in the relatively high number of women taking part in general with 37% women.

Action dedicated to high Fiscal and Reporting Standards We recognize our duty to act in the fiscal interests of the public, to avoid and declare all conflicts of interest in relation to the use of funds. We declare our dedication to transparent reporting of expenses and GAAP guidelines regarding fiscal reporting.

Code of Conduct well laid out, communicated and tested. Our Action intends to use and follow the Wikimedia Code of Conduct (https://foundation.wikimedia.org/wiki/Policy:Universal_Code_of_Conduct) in all of its actions and communications, the main tenements of this Code of Conduct are shared here

'In line with the Wikimedia mission, all who participate in Wikimedia projects and spaces will:

- Help create a world in which everyone can freely share in the sum of all knowledge
- Be part of a global community that will avoid bias and prejudice, and
- Strive towards accuracy and verifiability in all its work' (p. 1, Code of Conduct).

We believe our project has the opportunity to become an excellent COST Action, also paving the way for much greater opportunities, and a higher quality knowledge base, into the future.

Network of Proposers - Features

COST Inclusiveness Target Countries

66.67 %

Number of Proposers

19

Geographic Distribution of Proposers

Country	ITC/ non ITC/ other	Number of institutions from that country	Number of researchers from that country	Percentage of the proposing network
Armenia	ITC	1	1	5.26 %
Australia	other	1	1	5.26 %
Bulgaria	ITC	1	1	5.26 %
Croatia	ITC	1	1	5.26 %
Estonia	ITC	1	1	5.26 %
Germany	non ITC	2	2	10.53 %
Hungary	ITC	1	1	5.26 %
Italy	non ITC	2	2	10.53 %
Poland	ITC	4	4	21.05 %
Romania	ITC	1	1	5.26 %
Slovenia	ITC	1	1	5.26 %
Spain	non ITC	1	1	5.26 %
Switzerland	non ITC	1	1	5.26 %
United States	other	1	1	5.26 %

Gender Distribution of Proposers

63.2% Males

36.8% Females

Number of Young Researchers and Innovators

3

Core Expertise of Proposers: Distribution by Sub-Field of Science

21.1% Biological sciences

21.1% Computer and Information Sciences

21.1% Media and communications

10.5% Other humanities

5.3% Earth and related Environmental sciences

15.9% Other

5.3% Unspecified

Institutional distribution of Network of Proposers

73.7% Higher education, research-performing & associated organisations

15.8% Non-for profit organisation or association

5.3% Governmental organisation or agency (national, regional or local)

5.3% Business enterprise (large)

Higher education, research-performing & associated organisations:14

Non-for profit organisation or association:3

Governmental organisation or agency (national, regional or local):1

Business enterprise (large):1

COST Full Member (12) : Armenia, Bulgaria, Croatia, Estonia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland

International Partner (2) : Australia, United States

European RTD Organisation (0)

EU Institutions, Bodies, Offices and Agencies (EC/EU) (0)

International Organisation (0)

Network of Proposers - Details

Main Proposer's Details

Title: Dr

First Name: Brett

Gender: M

Last Name: Buttlere

**Is Young Researcher
and Innovator:** Yes

Institution: University of Warsaw

Category of country: COST Full Member

Sector: Higher education, research-
performing & associated
organisations

**Core Area of
Expertise:** Psychology (Databases,
data mining, data curation,
computational modelling)

Secondary Proposers' Details

Armenia

Dr Susanna Mkrtychyan (Institute For Informatics And Automation Problems Of The National Academy Of Sciences Of The Republic Of Armenia [Information Theory and Statistical Models Department])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Computer and Information Sciences: System research and DB

Gender: F

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Australia

Dr Gianluca Demartini (The University Of Queensland [School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Computer and Information Sciences: Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, multi agent systems

Gender: M

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Bulgaria

Prof Lyubomir Penev (Pensoft Publishers)

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Earth and related Environmental sciences: Terrestrial ecology, land cover change

Gender: M

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Croatia

Dr Natasa Jermen (Leksikografski zavod Miroslav Krleža [Office of the Director])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Media and communications: information sciences, bibliometrics, lexicography, encyclopaedic science

Gender: F

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Estonia

Mr Ivo Kruusamägi (MTÜ Wikimedia Eesti)

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise:

Gender: M

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: Yes

Germany

Dr Daniel Mietchen (Fiz Karlsruhe - Leibniz-institut Fur Informationsinfrastruktur Gmbh [Subject-Specific Services])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Biological sciences: Biodiversity, comparative biology

Gender: M

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Dr Sabine von Mering (Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science)

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Biological sciences: Plant biology, Botany

Gender: F

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Hungary

Dr János Tapolcai (Budapesti Muszaki Es Gazdasagtudományi Egyetem [Department of Telecommunications and Artificial Intelligence])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Computer and Information Sciences: Algorithms, distributed, parallel and network algorithms

Gender: M

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Italy

Dr Carlo Bianchini (Università Degli Studi Di Pavia [Department of Musicology and cultural heritage])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Media and communications: Library science

Gender: M

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Dr Rossana Morriello (University of Florence [Storia, archeologia, geografia, arte e spettacolo (SAGAS)])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Other humanities: Library and Information Science

Gender: F

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Poland

Dr Adam Płoszaj (UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI [Centre for European Regional and Local Studies EUROREG])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Sociology: Sociology of science

Gender: M

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Prof Dariusz Jemielniak (Akademia Leona Kozłminskiego)

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Economics and business: Organization studies

Gender: M

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Dr Katarzyna Makowska (Wikimedia Polska [Open Education])

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Biological sciences: Cell biology and molecular transport mechanisms

Gender: F

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: Yes

Romania

Dr Claudia Serbanuta (Asociația Comunității Viitorului)

Participating as Secondary Proposer

Core Expertise: Other humanities: Library and information science

Gender: F

Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

Slovenia

Dr Jernej Polajnar (National Institute of Biology [Department of Organisms and Ecosystems Research])

Participating as Secondary Proposer
Core Expertise: Biological sciences: Zoology, including animal behaviour
Gender: M
Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

 Spain

Dr Andreas Kaltenbrunner (Fundació Universitat Oberta de Catalunya)

Participating as Secondary Proposer
Core Expertise: Computer and Information Sciences: Social Media Mining, Social Network Analysis
Gender: M
Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

 Switzerland

Dr Iolanda Pensa (Scuola Universitaria Professionale Della Svizzera Italiana [Department for Environment Constructions and Design - Institute of design])

Participating as Secondary Proposer
Core Expertise: Media and communications: Media and communications, social aspects of information science and surveillance, socio-cultural communication
Gender: F
Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No

 United States

Dr Matthew Vetter (Indiana University of Pennsylvania [Language, Literature, & Writing])

Participating as Secondary Proposer
Core Expertise: Media and communications: Media and communications, social aspects of information science and surveillance, socio-cultural communication
Gender: M
Is Young Researcher and Innovator: No